

KADRLARNING NAZORATI BARQAROR IQTISODIYOT RIVOJLANISH ASOSI

КОНТРОЛЛИНГ ПЕРСОНАЛА КАК ОСНОВА УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ

PERSONNEL CONTROLLING AS A BASIS FOR SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada korxonalarining samarali ishlashi uchun omillardan biri sifatida xodimlarni nazorat qilish muammolari ko'rib chiqiladi. Kadrlar malakasini oshirish maqsadlari o'rganiladi, ular o'qitishni tashkilotlarning uzoq muddatli strategiyalari bilan bog'laydi. Zamonaviy korxonalarda kadrlar nazoratini rivojlantirishning asosiy tendentsiyalari aniqlandi.

Xodimlar, xodimlarni nazorat qilish, xodimlarni boshqarish.

В статье рассматриваются проблемы контроллинга персонала как одного из факторов эффективного функционирования предприятий. Изучены цели профессионального развития персонала, которые связывают обучение с долгосрочными стратегиями организаций. Определены основные тенденции развития контроллинга персонала на современных предприятиях.

Персонал, контроллинг персонала, управление персоналом

The article deals with the problems of personnel controlling as one of the factors of effective functioning of enterprises. The goals of professional development of personnel, which connect training with long-term strategies of organisations, are studied. The main tendencies of personnel controlling development at modern enterprises are defined.

Personnel, personnel controlling, personnel management

Instability of the external environment, acceleration of scientific and technological progress, increasing pressure from competitors make modern enterprises turn into more and more complex and flexible systems. According to experts, innovations related to the development of knowledge and skills of employees of a modern organisation, the development of their potential, have priority over innovations in the field of improving product properties, technology and production organisation, therefore, investments in personnel are the most reliable. That is why more and more companies consider personnel development as a priority option for decisions in the field of investment policy and strengthening of competitive advantages. Modern organisations should consider personnel training costs as investments in fixed capital, which allow the most efficient use of the latest technologies [1].

To ensure a high level of manageability, modern organisations require new methods that correspond to the dynamically changing external and internal environment. Personnel controlling is such a method designed to ensure long-term development of the enterprise.

Personnel controlling can be considered as a system of information-analytical and methodological support of managerial decision-making in the personnel management system in order to improve the efficiency of the organisation's functioning.

The objects of personnel controlling can be:

- personnel (qualitative and quantitative characteristics of personnel, labour potential of personnel, personnel costs);
- labour processes (organisation of labour activity of the personnel or working conditions);
- HR management functions (processes) (quantitative characteristics of processes, costs of realisation of HR management functions);
- personnel management system, its resource support.

Personnel controlling is differentiated into:

- determination of objectives (e.g., cost of personnel, scope of work);
- special functions of personnel management (e.g., professional development, attestation);
- methodological tools (e.g., personnel evaluation methods).

In the conditions of formation of the digital economy, the personnel of an organisation as a carrier of its human capital becomes a key resource that provides opportunities to create a product with high added value and increase the competitiveness of the organisation. Personnel are becoming the most profitable investment object capable of providing high returns through the creation of new knowledge and its implementation in the organisation's activities. At the same time, traditional approaches to personnel management and corresponding approaches to personnel cost management, characteristic of the industrial economy, have exhausted themselves and require revision [2].

Modern business is developing, competition is growing, and, as a consequence, organisations need to make more and more efforts to actively develop and be successful. This fact is also understood by modern domestic organisations, which pay more and more attention to the creation of a professional HR management system. Personnel training for the majority of organisations is now of particular importance. This is due to the fact that working in a market environment places high demands on the qualification level of personnel, their knowledge and skills, while they tend to lose their effectiveness in today's changing economy. Companies realise that personnel training and development is the most important condition for the successful functioning of any organisation, any business.

However, it is necessary to remember the fact that professional education, training and professional development of employees nowadays should be continuous and should be carried out throughout the entire labour activity. Of course, for continuous training to be effective, employees must be interested in it. The administration needs to create a climate favourable to training and develop the appropriate motivation to train their staff. The percentage of companies that have an employee training programme in place in 2023 has dropped from 84% to 73% compared to 2022. This is blamed on the economic crisis and companies' attempts to reduce staff costs. It also found that 52% of organisations that have retained education programmes provide staff training on a monthly basis, while 26% do so irregularly when required. Meanwhile, 17% of employers have partially suspended training processes, 15% have increased and expanded their programmes, and 4% have closed training completely. The study also found that almost all employees surveyed have either already completed their own training or are planning to go soon. A third of respondents said that the new knowledge had a significant impact on their career progression.

Thus, effective career and training management, in addition to direct profit growth, has a number of no less important positive consequences for the organisation, such as unlocking the potential of employees; uniting and improving the social and psychological climate of the team; increasing motivation; strengthening the loyalty of employees to the organisation; ensuring continuity in management; attracting new employees; forming desirable patterns of behaviour and the appropriate organisational culture conducive to successful achievement of the goals of the organisation; and improving the quality of the workforce.

Along with professionally organised processes of personnel selection and recruitment, stimulation, orientation and evaluation, one of the ways to help generate new ideas for business, develop and implement modern technologies and systems, and train highly professional, success-oriented employees, is to create a system of professional personnel training.

According to Western experts, innovations related to the development of knowledge and skills of employees of an entrepreneurial organisation, the development of their potential, have priority over innovations in the field of improving product properties, technology and production organisation, therefore, investments in personnel are the most reliable. Therefore, more and more companies consider personnel development as a priority option for investment policy decisions and strengthening of competitive advantages. Entrepreneurial organisations should consider personnel training costs as fixed capital investments that make the most efficient use of the latest technologies.

Thus, it can be stated that investing in personnel development brings more profit to an entrepreneurial organisation than investing in the improvement of production facilities, i.e. human resource can be defined as a key factor of efficiency in the use of all other resources available to the company. In addition, effective management of personnel development and training in addition to direct profit growth has a number of such, no less important, positive consequences for the organisation as unlocking the potential of employees; uniting and improving the social and psychological climate of the team; increasing motivation; strengthening the loyalty of employees to the organisation; ensuring continuity in management; attracting new employees; forming desirable patterns of behaviour and the appropriate organisational culture that contributes to the successful achievement of the company's goals; and improving the quality of the organisation's workforce.

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